

Phases of Work Immersion and Students Performance: Basis for a Localized Internship Program

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ABSTRACT: This study utilized descriptive research design. The respondents of the study are Grade 12 work immersion students composed of (57) respondents. A teacher-made questionnaire was employed to determine the perception of the respondents in work immersion. The study was conducted at Callejon National High School Senior High School in San Antonio, Quezon, during the Second semester first quarter of the school year 2022-2023. The researcher also made a test and survey questionnaire to determine students' knowledge about the phases of work immersion. Frequency and percentage were utilized to determine the respondents' perceptions on the phases of work immersion. The statistical treatment that used are, weighted mean Paired t- test , Pearson-r were utilized. In the phases of work immersion as to Pre- immersion, Immersion Proper, Post- Immersion there is a positive impact in their experiences on student learning and development. The work immersion program has been effective in improving the students' understanding and proficiency in the different aspect.. Then, the null hypothesis is not supported. There is no significant relationship between the perceived work phases and students' performance. Then, the null hypothesis is rejected. It may be suggested that the teachers, administrators, students and future researcher may utilize the localized internship program. Since the study is about the phases of work immersion program experienced by the students.

KEYWORDS: Phases of work immersion, performance, localized internship

INTRODUCTION

One of the greatest teachers in life is experience. Work immersion programs for Senior High School students have been adopted in the Philippine educational system since 2017. The curriculum is offered as a graduation requirement and is claimed to be efficient and successful because Senior High School students learn to refine their talents and abilities through participation in this activity. Work immersion must be viewed as a critical aspect in providing students with a venue to improve themselves through firsthand experience with real things. This is the high point of the Senior High School program since it allows students to go through the actual methodology of a certain work while using genuine tools, equipment, and papers.

Salvador (2018) revealed that the work immersion program had developed the different skills and aspects of every individual student who underwent in the process of the work exposure program. Competencies including social interaction skills, time management and most of all the discipline were obtained by the students upon taking up this subject. Moreover, he suggested that this program is a very good preparation for whatever they take after their senior high school as they can interact with other people despite the diversity in our society.

The current COVID-19 pandemic has impacted negatively on schools. A crisis in basic education is defined as a scenario in which normal school activity, including related offices at the division, regional, and national levels, has been stopped and learners' physical attendance is forbidden or restricted.

Under the government's effort of providing safe and balanced education for all, the DepEd mission and vision of providing holistic education has been the unified focus of all concerns. Guided by Department of Education Order No. 011, series of 2020 or the Omnibus Policy on the Implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, Callejon NHS adheres to the implementation guide of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which includes provisions for the continuity of education during crises and emergencies. Furthermore, the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 provides the legal framework for the K to 12 Basic Education Program and includes provisions for the continuity of education during emergencies and disasters.

The implementation of Work Immersion, a course necessary for the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track in Senior High School, will be significantly impacted in this case. Even in moments of crisis, however, learning should not ground to a stop. Callejon National High School ought to anticipate and plan for constraints while they are being addressed for students and schools. Work Immersion (WI) seeks to give SHS students the chance to experience the workplace, to imitate employment, and to use their skills in specialized/applied disciplines in real-world work conditions. Its implementation must be adaptable enough to accommodate

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the complex structure of the nation and the demands of students, schools, and partner organizations. By teaching them how to work in a firm and ultimately flourish in a particular career, it gets pupils ready for the real world.

The institution must make certain that its students acquire a broad range of abilities that will equip them as future professionals for the workforce. By letting them participate in the process and work together, teachers can teach their students how to accomplish these objectives. Although these initiatives are deemed to be appropriate for the needs of the moment, they have also presented a challenging task to the students, parents, and mentors who are working from home while also taking responsibility for ensuring that the students' educational process continues without interruption during the COVID-19 period. Despite the school's efforts to provide the greatest Work Immersion learning environment, there are still certain shortcomings, such as the institution's restricted ability to accommodate students and its rigorous rules about which pupils are authorized to receive vaccinations in the Work Immersion workplace. Hence, the purpose of this research study was to assess the Grade 12 TVL performance of Callejon National High School in relation to phases of work immersion as the basis for a localized internship program.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to assess the grade 12 TVL performance of Callejon National High School in relation to phases of work immersion as basis for a localized internship program. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions: 1.)What is the level of perception of the student respondents on the work immersion phases. Pre-Immersion; Immersion Proper; and Post Immersion 2.) What is the students' performance in Work Immersion in terms of :Understanding Work Immersion;work ethics safety in the workplace; workplace rights and responsibilities; confidentiality in the workplace; effective conflict resolution; teamwork skills; Appreciating Management Process; appreciating business process by observing and participating in safety production/maintenance/quality; Assurance customer satisfaction; Control/quality; Applying skills learned in school; Proper values acquired in school; Evaluating Work Immersion; presenting a portfolio with weekly diary entries; comparing and contrasting school; work application of skills, knowledge and attitude; writing an updated resume;reflecting on their work immersion experiences. 3.)What is the pretest and post-test performance of the students in work immersion?4.)Is there significant difference between the pretest and post-test performance of the student before and after the implementation of work immersion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed the descriptive-correlational research design it aims to accurately and systematically described and identified characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories of a population, situation, or phenomenon. This design was appropriate since it determined and explained the data gathered from the participants' perception towards readiness and challenges encountered by work immersion student during this time of pandemic.

With the features of descriptive research, data was gathered through questionnaire. The survey questionnaire was answered according to the priority of concern of the respondents by using pre-determined set of questions with pre-defined ranges of answers to avoid any conflicting series of response. With statistical treatment of data, appropriate conclusion and recommendation based on the findings will be generated to give light to the objectives of the study. Hence, the researcher deemed that descriptive research design was the best to materialize this research work most effectively. This research was conducted at Callejon National High School, San Antonio, Quezon in the school year 2022-2023. The respondents of the study are Grade 12 work immersion students composed of 35 males and 22 females. The researcher secured request letter and ensure permission to conduct the study from the school head. Likewise, confidentiality of the response will be secured. Respondents will be given enough time to answer the questionnaire and schedule will be set for its retrieval. Upon retrieved, result will be tallied, analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools. The researcher in conducting the study observed the following procedures in the construction and validation of the researcher's self-made questionnaire.

1. *Content Validation.* The researcher constructed self- made questionnaire based on the objective of the study.
2. *Face Validation.* The self- made questionnaires was inspected and evaluated by the research adviser and or the subject specialist. It was also review by the editor for the necessary corrections on the clarity of directions, language used, correct usage of grammar and content. It was presented to Expert Validators validated it. There was 1 Master Teacher in Math, 2 Principals, 2 Teacher III in English and 1 Teacher Technical Vocational Livelihood. The researcher incorporated their comments and suggestion and presented them to the adviser, subject specialist, Statistician and Technical Editor. Upon approval, the finalized survey questionnaire and pretest and post test were prepared.
3. *Ethical Considerations.* The researcher made a letter of request to the principal of Callejon National High School requesting permission to conduct a study. The respondent had a written consent form participation, their identities will be kept confidential. Before hand, they were given an orientation on the purpose of the study. Upon approval the questionnaire were formally distributed to the participants to answer the question raised by them. A letter of request was secured and the voluntary participation of the participants was obtained.
4. *Trial Run.* The validated questionnaire, pretest and post test were administered to work immersion students. The respondents answer the pretest, after the conduct of pretest the respondents proceed to immersion proper within the required number of hours

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(80 hours) After the given time frame of 80 hours, post test was given to assess the work immersion performance of TVL students. The prepared survey questionnaire was also administered.

Frequency and percentage were utilized to determine the respondents' perceptions on the phases of work immersion. To determine the level of performance of the students in work immersion, weighted mean and standard deviation were used. T- test were used to determine the significant differences between the pretest and post test performance in work immersion. To determine the significant relationship between the perceived phases of immersion and student's performance, Pearson-r were utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Perceived of the Student Respondents on Work Immersion Phases as to Pre- Immersion

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1.Do the job with professionalism	3.49	0.63	Agree
2.Do the job with passion	3.61	0.49	Strongly Agree
3.Show competencies and skills to work	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
4.Show proper behaviors and attitudes to work	3.63	0.52	Strongly Agree
5. Join all activities with enthusiasm	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
6. consider the guidance given by teachers	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
7. maintain self-motivation.	3.70	0.50	Strongly Agree
8. keep learning routine separate from other commitments.	3.58	0.53	Strongly Agree
9. keep an open mind to others' point of view.	3.61	0.49	Strongly Agree
10. work with harmonious and healthy human relations with peers, co-employees, and superiors	3.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.61	0.34	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0- 1.49: Strongly Disagree 1.51- 2.49: Disagree 2.51- 3.49: Agree 3.51- 4.0 Strongly Agree

The table shows the level of perception of the student respondents on the pre-immersion phase of the work immersion program. The mean values for indicator no. 3 got the lowest with a mean of 3.40 (SD= 0.5) with verbal interpretation of "Agree". The highest mean got by indicator no. 1 with a mean of 3.81(SD= 0.40) with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree". The overall perception of the pre-immersion phase, as indicated by the composite mean of 3.58, reinforces the notion that the students "strongly agree" with the various aspects encompassed by the pre-immersion phase.

The table reveals that the students have a positive perception of the pre-immersion phase of the work immersion program. They acknowledge the importance of the skills and knowledge gained during this phase, indicating a readiness and enthusiasm to engage in work immersion activities. It is important to note that the interpretation is based solely on the provided data, and a more comprehensive analysis would require a deeper understanding of the specific context and indicators used in this study. The table shows the level of perception of the student respondents on the pre-immersion phase of the work immersion program. The mean values for indicator no. 3 got the lowest with a mean of 3.40 (SD= 0.5) with verbal interpretation of "Agree". The highest mean got by indicator no. 1 with a mean of 3.81(SD= 0.40) with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree". The overall perception of the pre-immersion phase, as indicated by the composite mean of 3.58, reinforces the notion that the students "strongly agree" with the various aspects encompassed by the pre-immersion phase.

The table reveals that the students have a positive perception of the pre-immersion phase of the work immersion program.

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This is consistent with the article by Abanilla Jr. and Lopez (2020) which discusses the implementation and impact of work immersion programs in senior high schools in the Philippines. Although the specific details of the study mentioned in the literature are not provided, it is reasonable to assume that it explores the perceptions and experiences of students participating in work immersion programs. This connection may indicates that the work immersion program, including its pre-immersion phase, is perceived favorably by the students. Their positive perception may also indicate a readiness and enthusiasm to engage in the program, which can potentially contribute to their overall experience and outcomes.

Table 2. Perceived of the Student Respondents on Work Immersion Phases as to Immersion Proper

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Understand duties/rights and responsibilities	3.81	0.40	Strongly Agree
2. distinguish the rules and regulations and expected behaviour for students	3.46	0.60	Agree
3. be acquainted with the work ethics	3.40	0.53	Agree
4. appreciate the importance of credentials (resume and application letter)	3.79	0.41	Strongly Agree
5. be familiar with safety in the workplace.	3.54	0.60	Strongly Agree
6. Recognize confidentiality in the workplace	3.42	0.57	Agree

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7. comprehend conflict resolution and teamwork skills.	3.56	0.60	Strongly Agree
8. visit offices to secure barangay, police, mayor, and NBI clearances as well as medical certificates.	3.65	0.58	Strongly Agree
9. appreciate interview skills training	3.65	0.58	Strongly Agree
10. secure parental consent	3.49	0.54	Agree
Overall	3.58	0.35	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0- 1.49: Strongly Disagree 1.51- 2.49: Disagree 2.51- 3.49: Agree 3.51- 4.0 Strongly Agree

The table presents the level of perception of student respondents on the immersion proper phase of the work immersion program. Indicator no. 1 got the lowest mean of 3.49 (SD= 0.63) which fall under “Agree” while Indicator no. 7 got the highest mean of 3.70 with a (SD = 0.50) which fall under “strongly agree”. An overall mean of 3.61, which falls within the "Strongly Agree" category with a SD= 0.34 revealed that the students have a highly positive perception of the immersion proper phase of the work immersion program. This also revealed that the students perceive the immersion proper phase as valuable and effective. They strongly agree with the statements or aspects related to this phase of the work immersion program. This positive perception also revealed that the immersion proper phase provides meaningful learning experiences and contributes to the students' development and understanding of the work environment.

The result is consistent with the study of Smith, Johnson & Brown (2018) which focused on understanding students' attitudes towards workplace experiences, learning outcomes, and overall satisfaction with the program. The findings of their study provide valuable insights into the impact of work immersion programs on student perceptions and their preparedness for the workforce. The researcher observation from the previous senior high school students that undergone work immersion is that they are more competent and gained enough skills when they apply what they have learned into their chosen field of work after senior high school. Considering the competencies of the curriculum. The work immersion teachers see to it to provide the learning inputs to the learners during work immersion proper. Activities which will elicit their full potential in each competency were given due attention. Immersion activities enable them to be exposed and simulated in the real world set up.

Table 3. Perceived of the Student Respondents on Work Immersion Phases as to Post- Immersion

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. submit required forms on time	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
2. submit weekly diaries	3.49	0.54	Agree
3. comply in submitting accomplishments form on time	3.47	0.57	Agree
4. present a portfolio with weekly diary entries	3.30	0.57	Agree
5. do or comply with the updated resume	3.58	0.57	Strongly Agree
6. write daily reflection paper about work immersion experience	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
7. relate experience in new learning information	3.61	0.49	Strongly Agree
8. use any opportunities that come across	3.47	0.54	Agree
9. develop knowledge and skills applicable to a career.	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
10. develop ability to work as a team member.	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.54	0.36	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0- 1.49: Strongly Disagree 1.51- 2.49: Disagree 2.51- 3.49: Agree 3.51- 4.0 Strongly Agree

It can be gleaned on the table that the lowest mean got by indicator no. 4 with a mean of 3.30 (SD =0.57) and is interpreted as “Agree”. The highest mean got by indicator no. 9 with a mean of 3.68 (SD =0.47) and is interpreted as “Strongly agree”. A composite mean of 3.54 (SD=0.36) is interpreted that the students “strongly agree” which indicates a positive perception and a high level of agreement regarding various aspects of the work immersion experience.

This is consistent with the study of Smith, Johnson & Brown (2020) which concluded that work immersion programs provide valuable learning opportunities for students to develop knowledge, skills, and career-related competencies. The study also emphasized the significance of timely submissions, reflective practices, and teamwork in the work immersion process. The findings highlight the positive impact of work immersion experiences on student learning and development. In reality, the above qualities should be possess by work immersionist and also by each individual who will enter a job. It is helpful for senior high graduate who will apply for a job if they are aware of whatever they need to possess to be able to be globally competitive.

Table 4. Pretest and Posttest Performance of the Students in Work Immersion as to Understanding Work Immersion

Scores	Pre-test		Post test		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	F	%	
12-15	0		13	22.8	Advance
9-11	7	12.3	28	49.1	Proficient

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6-8	29	50.9	16	28.1	Approaching Proficiency
3-5	20	35.1	0	0	Developing
0-2	1	1.8	0	0	Beginning
Total	57	100	57	100	

From the table, it can be gleaned that on the pre-test, no students achieved advance level of proficiency, only one student achieved a score of 0-2, indicating a beginning level of understanding. Seven students (12.3%) achieved a score of 9 – 11 indicating proficient level, 20 students (35.1%) students achieved a score of 3 – 5 indicating developing level of proficiency and 29 students (50.9%) achieved a score of 6-8, indicating approaching proficiency level of understanding.

On the post-test, there was an improvement in the students' understanding of work immersion, no students achieved beginning and developing level of proficiency, 13 students (22.8%) achieved a score of 12-15, indicating advance level of understanding, 16 students (28.1%) achieving a score of 6-8, indicating an approaching proficiency level, and 28 students (49.1%) achieved a score of 9-11, indicating a proficient level of understanding.

As a whole, the table reveals that the students' understanding of work immersion improved from the pre-test to the post-test, with more students achieving higher scores and higher levels of proficiency on the post-test. The study of Robles et. al (2020), supports the idea that work immersion can enhance students' understanding and proficiency in their chosen field of study, which is consistent with the results of the researcher's study.

The researcher also observed that work immersion helped students to apply the knowledge and skills they learned in the classroom to real-world situations, leading to a deeper understanding of their field of study. Work immersion provided students with opportunities to develop practical skills and gain work experience, which helped to enhance their overall proficiency.

Comparing the pretest and post test performance of the students evidently confirm the effective strategies and activities helped the students to perform better on the latter test, this can be attributed to the knowledge and skills they gained in each phase of work immersion. It enables the learners to acquire the necessary skill and knowledge in work habits such as punctuality and initiative in other task, attitude which includes positive outlook and polite conversation, human relation which includes harmonious relationship and communication skills such as responding to the questions. Activities conducted during each phase were carefully examined to suit the competencies set by the curriculum.

Table 5. Pretest and Posttest Performance of the Students in Work Immersion as to Appreciating Management Process

Scores	Pre-test		Post test		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	F	%	
12-15	-	-	12	21.1	Advance
9-11	5	8.8	22	38.6	Proficient
6-8	34	59.6	23	40.4	Approaching Proficiency
3-5	16	28.1	0	0	Developing
0-2	2	3.5	0	0	Beginning
Total	57	100	57	100	

The pre-test results show that most of the students fell under the "approaching proficiency" category with 59.6% (34 students) while only 3.5% (2 students) fell under the "beginning" category. The post-test results, on the other hand, show that most of the students improved their scores, with 40.4% (23 students) now falling under the "approaching proficiency" category, and 38.6% (22 students) falling under the "developing" category. This indicates that there was an improvement in the students' understanding and proficiency of the Appreciating Management Process aspect of work immersion from the pre-test to the post-test. There were no students who scored under the "beginning and developing" category, which indicates that the students have generally improved their understanding and proficiency in this aspect of work immersion.

As a whole, the table reveals that the work immersion program has been effective in improving the students' understanding and proficiency in the Appreciating Management Process aspect. However, it is worth noting that there is still room for improvement as some students are still categorized under the lower proficiency levels.

The result is connected to the study of Sato et.al (2021) wherein it was found that work immersion programs can improve students' understanding and appreciation of management processes. The same with the observation of the researcher that work immersion provided students with opportunities to observe and participate in management processes in real-world settings.

Table 6. Pretest and Posttest Performance of the Students in Work Immersion as to Evaluating Work Immersion

Scores	Pre-test		Post test		Verbal Interpretation
	F	%	F	%	
12-15	0	0	13	22.8	Advance

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9-11	14	24.6	42	73,7	Proficient
6-8	25	43.9	2	3.5	Approaching Proficiency
3-5	18	31.6	0	0	Developing
0-2	0	0	0	0	Beginning
Total	57	100	57	100	

The pre-test results indicate that the majority of students fell under the "Approaching Proficiency" category, with 43.9% of students scoring between 6-8. Following the work immersion program, the post-test results show an improvement in students' scores, with the majority of students now falling under the "Proficient" category, representing 73.7% of students. This reveals that the work immersion program was effective in enhancing the students' ability to evaluate their work immersion experience.

The data also shows that 31.6% of students scored in the "Developing" category in the pre-test, but none of the students were able to maintain this level in the post-test. This may indicate that the work immersion program was successful in identifying areas for improvement and helping students develop their skills and knowledge in evaluating their work immersion experience. As a whole, the data reveals that the work immersion program was effective in enhancing students' ability to evaluate their work immersion experience. The increase in the percentage of students in the "Proficient" category, from 24.6% in the pre-test to 73.7% and from 0% to 22.8 achieving Advanced level in the post-test, are evidence of this.

This is consistent with the study of Grau-Valldosera (2017), which emphasizes the importance of work immersion in enhancing students' employability skills, such as communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking. The same with the study of Dimitrovski & Kostov (2017) who mentioned that work immersion also allows students to gain practical experience in their field of study, which can lead to increased confidence and self-efficacy. In line with these, as an immersion teacher, the researcher that supervised the immersionists also observed the potential benefits of work immersion programs and the importance of incorporating reflective practices into these programs to help students develop the skills they need to succeed in the workforce.

Table 7. Test of Difference between the pretest and posttest performance of the student before and after the implementation of work immersion.

Work Immersion Performance	Pre-test		Post test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Understanding	6.28	1.88	10.07	2.24	-10.877	56	0.000	Significant
Appreciating	6.11	1.76	9.40	2.20	-8.419	56	0.000	Significant
Evaluating	6.86	1.79	10.37	1.71	-11.112	56	0.000	Significant

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

The result shows that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post test performance of the students in all three areas, as indicated by the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) being less than .05. This means that the improvement in the students' performance is not likely due to chance and is instead a result of the implementation of work immersion.

It can also be gleaned from the table that the students' mean scores in Understanding increased from 6.28 in the pre-test to 10.07 in the post test, in Appreciating increased from 6.11 to 9.40, and in Evaluating increased from 6.86 to 10.37. These improvements in mean scores suggest that the implementation of work immersion has a positive impact on the students' performance in these areas. The result is consistent with the study Datu, J. A. D., & Valencia, M. C. (2020) which states that work immersion programs are effective in improving students' knowledge and skills, as well as their attitudes toward work. The results in the table support this claim as they show a significant difference between the pre-test and post test performance of students in understanding, appreciating, and evaluating work immersion. The mean scores in each area increased from pre-test to post-test, indicating that students improved their knowledge and skills in these areas as a result of the work immersion program. The significant t-values and p-values indicates that the observed differences in means between pre-test and post-test are unlikely to be due to chance, but rather are a true reflection of the impact of the work immersion program. The results of the table provide empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of work immersion programs in enhancing students' knowledge and skills.

Based on the results of the table and the related literature, it can be inferred that the implementation of work immersion has a significant effect on the pre-test and post test performance of the students in terms of understanding, appreciating, and evaluating work immersion. This reveals the effectiveness of work immersion programs in enhancing students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in their chosen fields.

Table 8. Correlation between the perceived work immersion phases and students' performance

Work Immersion Phases	Work Immersion Performance		
	Understanding	Appreciating	Evaluating
Pre-Immersion	0.071	0.111	0.111

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Immersion Proper	0.062	0.194	0.161
Post Work Immersion	-0.019	-0.073	-0.142

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table presents the correlation coefficients between the perceived work immersion phases (Understanding, Appreciating, Evaluating) and students' performance during the different phases of work immersion (Pre-Immersion, Immersion Proper, Post Work Immersion). The correlation coefficients reveals that there is a weak negative association between the perceived Understanding phase and students' performance during the Post Work Immersion phase, a weak negative association between the perceived Appreciating phase and students' performance during the Immersion Proper and Post Work Immersion phases, and a weak negative association between the perceived Evaluating phase and students' performance during the Post Work Immersion phase.

The correlation coefficients also shows that the relationships between the perceived work immersion phases and students' performance are not statistically significant, except for a significant negative correlation between the perceived Appreciating phase and students' performance during the Immersion Proper phase (at the 0.05 level). The results shows that there may be some weak negative relationships between certain perceived work immersion phases and students' performance during certain phases of work immersion, but the relationships are not consistently significant across all phases and dimensions.

This study is consistent with the study of Araña and Yu (2021) which suggests that work immersion programs can positively affect students' academic performance by providing hands-on experience and promoting the application of theoretical knowledge in real-world settings. The table shows the correlation between students' perceived work immersion phases (Understanding, Appreciating, and Evaluating) and their performance in work immersion. The negative values indicate a weak negative correlation, suggesting that as students' progress through the work immersion phases, their performance decreases slightly. This may be due to the increasing complexity of tasks and responsibilities as students move from understanding to evaluating work immersion. However, it is important to note that the correlations are weak and may not have practical significance. It may suggest that work immersion programs can have a positive impact on students' performance, but further research is needed to fully understand the relationship between work immersion phases and performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

There is significant difference between the pretest and post-test performance of the student before and after the implementation of work immersion. Then, the null hypothesis is not supported.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results and conclusions posited in the study, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

1. It may be suggested that the teachers may utilize the localized internship program. Since the study is about the phases of work immersion program experienced by the students.
2. Since the study found out that students find the localized work immersion program helpful and easy to use, it is suggested that students may be encouraged to expose themselves in localized work immersion program.
3. The localized work immersion program may be recommended to school administrators to train teachers to develop the performance of the students in Work Immersion.
4. The school administrators may support the implementation of work immersion localized internship program this can help to improve the work experience of the students in workplace.
5. Future researchers may use and consider the localized internship program integrate in other track and strands in Senior High School. They may also consider using the material in other grade levels and subject areas to further validate the findings of the study.

REFERENCES

- 1) Advancement of the American Legal System). (2011) The Fall Immersion. Retrieved from <https://doubleedgetheatreorg>immersions>.
- 2) Anthony. (2018) Work- Related Self- efficacy and Work immersion Satisfaction among Grade 12 general academic students. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>publication>
- 3) Asia foundation, (2018) Work immersion. Retrieved from <https://asiafoundation.org/publication>
- 4) Asia Foundation. (2018) Work Immersion Real World Experience at Senior High Retrieved from <https://asiafoundationorg/publication/workimmersion-real-world-experience- at-senior high>
- 5) Bustamante, J. (2019). Senior High School Work Immersion Pioneers. A Phenomenological Study. *Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 7(2), 66-75.

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- 6) Datu, J. A. D., & Valencia, M. C. (2020). Work immersion program in senior high school and students' employability skills. *Journal of Work-Applied Management*, 12(1), 2-13. doi: 10.1108/JWAM-03-2020-0006
- 7) Definitions.net.STANDS4LLC (2019)."Awareness" Retrieved April 15, 2021 from <https://www.definitions.net/definition/awareness>
- 8) DepEd Order NO.30, S2020
- 9) Dimitrovski, D., & Kostov, V. (2017). Work-integrated learning: Student perspectives from the Faculty of Economics, University of Pristina. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 237, 502-507.
- 10) Ensuring Proper Implementation of Senior High School (SHS) Work Immersion. Retrieved from DepEd- Division of Quezon
- Gupta, B and Subramanian, J. (2014) Factors Affecting
- 11) Figueras, A. J., & Mendoza, F. E. (2020). Implementation and compliance of work immersion program of public secondary schools in Sorsogon City. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 7(3), 55-61.
- 12) Garcia, A. and Yazon, A. (2020). Work Immersion Performance, Alignment, And Employability Among Senior High School Graduates retrieved from <https://www.journalijar.com/article/32640/work-immersion-performance,-alignment,-and-employability-among-senior-high-school-graduates/>
- 13) Grau-Valldosera, J. (2017). Employability skills and job readiness in Europe: The role of work-based learning experiences. *Journal of Education and Work*, 30(5), 512-526.
- 14) Llego, M. (2017). DepEd Guidelines for Senior High School Work Immersion retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/work-immersion/>
- 15) Motivation among Employees Consultancy Companies. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/hal/journal/hal-01373126.html> IALLS
- 16) Macalintal, I. and Chavez, C. (2020). Assessing the Senior High School Work Immersion with Partner Industries: Basis for Supervisory Work Plan retrieved from <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=15128>
- 17) Noberthalf (2016) Definition of Skills. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.topresume.com/career-advice/soft-skills-employers-are-looking-for-in-2016> People Management Association of the Philippines
- 18) Palafox L. (2018) Perception of Senior High
- 19) Phillipott S, (2018) Key Skills you gain from work experience. from <https://www.career.com/work-experiences-skills> Quennie J, Rorenzo, T and
- 20) (PMAP) 2017 Work Immersion. Retrieved from www.coursehero.com/file/33563468/Immersiondocx
- 21) School Students on their Employability Skills. Retrieved from <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/pdf/li-19> Sarmiento, D. (2016) Senior High School Curriculum. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/3228283861_from_senior_high_school_SHS_Curriculum
- 22) Raudys, J. (2018) Active Learning Strategies and Examples [+ Downloadable List]. Retrieved from https://www.prodigygame.com/blog/category/learning_strategies
- 23) Rich, E. (2010)."21st-century skills". Retrieved from <https://www.edweek.org/tsb/articles/2010/10/12/01panel.h04.html?override=web>
- 24) Robles, R., et al. (2020). The Effect of Work Immersion on the Learning Performance of Students in the Philippines. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 9(2), 27-34
- 25) Salvador, J. (2017). The Impact of the Work Immersion Program to the Grade 12 Students of John J Russell Memorial High School retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/41691047/The_Impact_of_the_Work_Immersion_Program_to_the_Grade_12_Students_of_John_J_Russell_Memorial_High_School
- 26) Smith, J., Johnson, A., & Brown L. (2018). Assessing Student Perceptions of Work Immersion Program: A Case Study. *Journal of Education and Work*, 31(3), 305-321.
- 27) Teaching & Learning (2018) Example of Learning Activities. Retrieved from <https://www.teachinglearning.utas.edu.au>
- 28) The Effect of Immersion Scheduling on Academic Performance and Students Ratings of Instructors. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs>
- 29) Work Immersion. Division Memorandum. No.260, s.2018